

Malnutrition and Inequality among the Vulnerable Social Groups:
A Study of Two Villages

Gummadi Sridevi¹, Amalendu Jyotishi², Dontha Prashanth³

Abstract

This paper examines malnutrition issues among the socially vulnerable group through the study of two villages in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana. By juxtaposing incidences of malnutrition along with other important parameters of inequality, namely, income, access to land and credit, we identify the genesis of malnutrition is strongly visible in economic inequality and reflects prominently among the Scheduled Castes who are among the most vulnerable social groups. By conducting a census like survey in these two villages, we find that malnutrition issues are strongly intertwined in economic and social classes. Therefore, delineating issues of economic access and social marginalization would not result in effectively addressing malnutrition issues.

Keywords: Malnutrition, Social Vulnerability, Economic Inequality, Poverty

¹Associate Professor, School of Economics, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad India. E-mail: gummadi645@gmail.com

² Professor, School of Development, Azim Premji University, Bangalore, India.

³ Research Scholar, School of Economics, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad, India.

Introduction

In India, high incidence of poverty and disparity in access to nutritious food are found among particular socio-religious and gender groups. Both in rural and urban areas, poverty and malnutrition rates are high and urban areas are among the new epicenters of poverty and hunger. While food production and the market are critical dimensions generally well discussed in literature, there is little knowledge on how food reaches the plate. The knowledge base is further inadequate in terms of various pathways, negotiations, choices and cultures influencing who eats what and why.

What are the constraints in availing and accessing nutritious food? What role do the state and other institutions play in addressing undernutrition? Economic access to food depends on the purchasing power of the household, which in turn depends on the regular employment, access to land, prices of food grains and food distribution. Mere availability of food grains will have little relevance if people do not possess purchasing power to procure them for their consumption. Though there are several studies available at global, macro and meso levels, literature is scanty at household level in-depth analysis on marginalized groups.

Several questions emerge including, what characterizes the social vulnerability of various social groups and its impact on nutritional security of the households. Similarly, although studies have documented various adaptation options of households, very few studies have looked into the factors at household levels that drive the decision to undertake a particular adaptation strategy during the food insecurity situation. This study is an attempt to fill the gaps by examining the social vulnerability, nutritional security, and adaptation among the marginalized households in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana.

Context

India produced 291.95 MT (metric tonnes) of food grains in 2019-20 yet 69% of deaths of children under the age of five have been attributed to malnutrition by UNICEF in state of the world's children report (UNICEF study has found that 8.8 lakh children in India below the age of five died prematurely in 2018. Of those, 69% died of malnutrition). Nearly 690 million people are undernourished, 144 million children suffer from stunting- which is a sign of chronic undernutrition. 47 million children suffer from wasting, a sign of acute undernutrition in 2018, 5.3 million children died before their fifth birthdays, in many cases as a result of undernutrition (GHI, 2020).

India, one of the bottommost countries, is ranked 102nd among 117 countries according to the Global Hunger Index, 2019. In 2020 Global Hunger Index, India ranks 94th out of the 107 countries with a score of 27.2, India has a level of hunger that is serious. NITI Aayog released report during June 2021 highlighting the fact that 11 states, including the most populous ones, scored less than 50 out of 100 in reaching zero hunger. Andhra Pradesh and Telangana scored less than 50 out of 100 in reaching Zero Hunger, but interestingly in overall performance of the state Andhra Pradesh is in third position. The pandemic has threatened India's food security landscape across all four indicators: availability, access, stability, and utilization. It could in turn further intensify the existing problem of malnutrition among women and children.

According to NFHS-4 more than 35% of Indian children under five are underweight, over 38% are stunted, and more than half of all children are anaemic. Given the magnitude of the problem, there is a need to understand the food value chain, especially at the point of consumption and assess its availability, accessibility, utilization and stability [the four critical dimensions of food and nutrition security (FNS)].

The main emphasis of the SDG is to reduce malnutrition and provide food security to all (Goal 2 by 2030, Zero Hunger and all forms of malnutrition). 40% of children in Telangana and Andhra Pradesh are malnourished majority belongs to vulnerable groups. Among these groups, the prevalence of stunting is highest amongst children from STs (41%), followed by SCs (35.2%) and OBCs (31.6%). Women whose Body Mass Index (BMI) is below normal ($<18.5 \text{ kg/m}^2$) is highest among ST (21.1) followed by OBC (16.1) and SC (15.0) anaemia among children in the age group of 6-59 months across social groups is very high based on NFHS-5 for Andhra Pradesh. For Telangana state these percentages are high though NFHS-5 data is not yet available for the state.

Apart from indirect interventions, there is a need to directly focus on nutritional deficiencies and address them in timely manner. A paradigm shift from caloric consumption to consumption of micronutrient and protein-rich food as well as the four pillars namely availability, accessibility, utilization and stability through direct and indirect modes of targeting are crucial. While indirect means would include understanding bottlenecks and improving the production and value chain processes of nutrition-rich food products, the direct method would involve provisioning of adequate nutritious food to malnourished groups.

Undernourishment and related health issues have been one of the dreaded realities of India. Across the states the picture varies according to the intensity of poverty, literacy, low density of health infrastructure and state support policies. Table: 1 shows the rank correlation coefficient of nutritional indicators among states between NFHS- 3 and NFHS-4. All values of rank correlation coefficients are high and positive, implying that there is not much change in the relative status of states on child nutritional outcome over the period.

As compared to wasting, the rank correlation coefficient of stunting and underweight are very high and positive. The states

that witnessed a high percentage of stunting and underweight children during NFHS-3 period could not make any dent even during the NFHS-4. Despite overall progress in stunting, wasting and underweight in the country, the relative status of states remains the same.

Table: 1 Rank Correlation Coefficient of Nutritional Indicators

Nutritional indicators	Rank correlation coefficient between NFHS-3 and NFHS-4
Stunting	0.888**
Wasting	0.616**
Underweight	0.911**

Notes:
 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)
 *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Source: Calculated from NFHS 3 and 4

Figure 1: Nutritional Status of Children under age 5 (NFHS 4 & 5):
 Stunted

Chart: Gummadi Sridevi; Source: NFHS; Created with data wrapper

Figure 2: Nutritional Status of Children under 5 (NFHS 4 & 5):
Underweight

Chart: Gummadi Sridevi; Source: NFHS; Created with data wrapper

Figure 3: Nutritional Status of Children under 5 (NFHS 4 & 5): Wasted

Chart: Gummadi Sridevi; Source: NFHS; Created with data wrapper

NFHS 5 fact sheets for 22 states/Union Territories (UT) shows, chronic undernutrition has increased in 13 states/UTs, whereas, underweight has increased in 16 states/UTs despite ambitious state support programs like *Poshan Abhiyaan*, malnutrition is still high.

Table: 2 Grouping of States Based on Stunting

States	NFHS-5 (2019-20)	CNNS (2019)	NFHS-4 (2015-16)	NFHS-3 (2005-06)	NFHS-2 (1998-99)
Low nutritional insecurity	Mizoram, Kerala, J&K, Himachal Pradesh	Mizoram, Kerala, J&K, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Telangana	Mizoram, Kerala, J&K Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Telangana	Kerala, Tamil Nadu	Kerala, Tamil Nadu
Medium nutritional insecurity	Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Telangana, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Gujarat	Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Uttarakhand, Haryana, Odisha, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Rajasthan	Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Uttarakhand, Haryana, Odisha, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Rajasthan	J&K, Punjab, HP, Mizoram	Mizoram, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, J&K, Punjab, Maharashtra
High nutritional insecurity	Bihar	Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar	Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar	Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Karnataka, Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Odisha, Haryana, Maharashtra, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Chhattisgarh, Bihar, UP	HP, West Bengal, Gujarat, Odisha, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Bihar, Pradesh

Source: Calculated from NFHS Reports (Various rounds), CNNS 2019.

Acute malnutrition is a complex socio-cultural problem that lies at the interplay of inequitable access to nutritious foods and health services, sub-optimal ‘infant and young child-feeding practices’ (IYCF) including breastfeeding, low maternal education, poor access to clean water and sanitation, poor hygiene practices, food insecurity and unpreparedness for emergencies.

The various rounds of NFHS provide the major source of macro-level statistics on nutritional status of children under five in India. Often, aggregate results may be misleading as the severity of malnutrition at the disaggregated level may be masked by the average and may fail to capture the real cause of the problem at the micro-level. Within a state, there are inter-district disparities in nutritional outcomes and the health and nutritional status of vulnerable communities are precarious. Most of the studies at micro-level focused on the high burden malnutrition states in India. Hence, it has not attracted much interest of researchers to analyze the nutritional status of children in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana at Anganwadi and household level. In this context, studying the incidents of malnutrition among vulnerable social groups in a micro context becomes more relevant.

Methods

Primary data was collected from one village each from Telangana and Andhra Pradesh. The villages were identified on the basis of two characteristics: 1) Consisting highest proportion of Scheduled Caste (SC) population, 2) Population engaged in agriculture. In the state of Telangana, district of Karimnagar is identified as a district with highest SC population. Within Karimnagar, Kataram Mandal has been ranked highest in terms of having higher proportion of SC population constituting 33.85% of the total population.

Within Kataram Mandal, Odipilavancha village panchayat is ranked highest with SC constituting 53.12% of the total population. The village has a majority of its population dependent on agriculture, with paddy and cotton being the principal crops.

In the state of Andhra Pradesh, district of Prakasam is identified as a district with highest proportion of SC population. In Prakasam District, Tangutur Mandal has the highest proportion of SC with 37.8% to the total population. In Tangutur Mandal, Velagapoodi village panchayat consisted highest proportion of SC population of 64.71% of total population constituting Velagapoodi Village had dismal amount of agriculture dependence, on the contrary most of the area was operated under sericulture. Hence, a next village Karumanchi ranking second in terms of proportion of SC to the total population was chosen, with a majority of population engaged in cultivation of paddy, Bengalgram and tobacco.

Table 3: Characteristics of the case study villages

Village	No. of HHs	Population	SC (HHs)	ST (HHs)	OBC (HHs)	Other (HHs)	Agricultural activity
Karumanchi (Andhra Pradesh)	746*	1048	402 (53.89)	38 (5.09)	163 (21.85)	143 (19.17)	Bengal Gram, Tobacco, Paddy
Odipilavancha (Telangana)	370*	1472	215 (58.11)	32 (8.61)	82 (22.2)	41 (11.1)	Paddy and cotton

Notes:
 *Total Number of Households according to Census 2011 is 1048. But at the time of our survey 746 households were present and the remaining households migrated to nearby towns. ** Similarly, total Households according to Census 2011 is 408. However, at the time of the survey 370 households were present in the village.

To assess the nutritional and health outcome of women and children, direct methods of nutritional assessment, namely anthropometric and dietary evaluation methods, were used. Inputs on weight, height and age of children are used to compute anthropometric failures among children in the study area, using WHO child growth standards. The nutritional status of women is gauged, based on BMI.

Access to Food and Incidents of Malnutrition at Household Level in the two villages

Although households are often the primary income recipients and are always the units for which we observe consumption, there exists indifference in the allocation to individual members in the household. To examine the question whether and to what extent allocation within the household differ according to the gender and social groups, we investigated the access to food and nutrition at household level.

Two types of measures have been used to quantify the food distribution within a household:

- Food intake by individuals converted into nutrients.
- Height, weight and age measures for anthropometric indices.

The consumption of rice and other cereals by the households during the reference period (7 days preceding the date of the survey) is considered for the analysis. All the households consume rice, vegetables edible oil in all the seasons. Both quality and quantity of rice consumed differed across levels of living of the households.

In order to obtain a variation across different classes we have taken consumption of cereals across different land holding groups for the analysis. The poor households not possessing white card/food security card are the worst affected during the slack seasons. By the land ownership holding, consumption of cereals

is lowest among the less than one-acre class and highest among the households having more than 10 acres of land (Table4). This clearly shows that any change in income across the board will not change the relative consumption of food by the poor households.

Table 4: Per capita monthly consumption of cereals by different types of land holding households in both the villages (in kilogram (kg))

Land size (acres)	Odipilavancha			Karumanchi		
	APL	BPL	NPC	APL	BPL	NPC
Up to 1	18.1	15.1	12.9	19.1	14.4	14.7
1 to 2.5	19.1	15.6	16.3	18.2	1.6	11.8
2.5 to 5	20.3	18.6	16.9	21.0	17.8	16.9
5 to 10	21.8	NA	NA	22.3	NA	NA
> 10	22.5	NA	NA	24.7	NA	NA
Total	20.2	16.7	15.8	21.8	17.1	15.6

Note:
 APL – Above Poverty Line, BPL – Below Poverty Line, NPC – Not Possessing Card, NA – Not Applicable

Source: Field survey, 2018

Table 5: Percent of households getting enough food every day in Karumanchi and Odipilavancha (in %)

Social group	Throughout the year	Only some months of the year	Infrequently
Karumanchi			
SCs	60	22	18
ST	45	40	15
OBC	80	15	5
Others	92	6	2
Total	65	25	10
Odipilavancha			
SC	55	30	15
ST	48	42	10
OBC	84	14	2
Others	90	8	2
Total	60	27	13

Source: Field survey, 2018

Frequency of meals per day is taken as an indicator of food insecurity at household level. Table 18 shows the food availability status for each social group. Only 60% of SC and 45% of ST groups said that they are getting enough food throughout the year in Karumanchi.

During our fieldwork a common response from the respondents from poor group was that “when we have, we eat, when we don’t have, we don’t eat”. This reveals a very simple adjustment process indeed. It substantiates our hypothesis that female-headed households have more food insecurity problem compared to male-headed households. Within the households, female members generally go hungry when the available quantity of food is inadequate. This adequately underscores the fact that food insecurity is sharper in the context of gender.

The calorie intake for a sample household was derived by converting the quantities of food items consumed by the individuals into equivalent amounts of calories by using standard conversion factors (NSSO, 26th round). We have used the 2,000 calories per consumer unit per day, as a standard against which actual observed calorie intakes are compared and that of fat and protein is 27.61 grams (gm) and 48.17 gm. Calorie intake is different across the social groups and between the two villages, due to their food habits, income and access to Public Distribution System (PDS).

Most of the poverty studies in India are based on nutritional adequacy, but what does an average ‘nutritional adequacy’ really mean has been a debatable issue. Sukhatme (1980) argued that there is a range of dietary intake that may be considered adequate among adults depending on activity levels, climate, etc. Calorie intake is low among the SC and ST households in both the villages that reflect the food insecurity at household level.

Table 6: Calorie Protein and Fat intake at household level per day in Karumanchi and Odipilavancha

Social group	Karumanchi			Odipilavancha		
	Calories (Kcal)	Protein (gm)	Fat (gm)	Calories (Kcal)	Protein (gm)	Fat (gm)
SC	1890.1	42.2	23.8	1730	40.2	22.8
ST	1710.6	32.8	20.4	1700.6	34.8	21.4
OBC	2103.4	48.0	28.3	2150.4	49.0	29.3
Others	2175.1	57.8	29.8	2260.1	49.8	29.8

Source: Field survey, 2018

While per-capita calorie intake reflects current consumption, the question of quantity does not address many other elements of the complicated notion of “food security,” such as quality and micronutrient sufficiency, vulnerability, and trends in consumption over time. Generally, female members of household do not have control on food budget and therefore, they come at the end of the queue to receive low calorie diets. By control, here we mean decisions about food budget in food distribution. Control can be exercised over material stocks, and over their preparation of food within the household from the raw material stage to that of ready for consumption product.

In the selected villages, the male heads of household enjoyed sole control of market decisions relating to domestic food in nearly 78% of the cases, and jointly with the wife in another 22%. There was no significant association between female participation in labour market, their earnings, and the control over food expenditure and purchase decisions. At the same time there was an association between the gender of food controller and their social group. When we looked into the order in which the family avails food consumption, male member or head of the household is given the first priority. In all the social groups adult male is given the first priority (85%), women eat last, by choice, so that male members of the households get sufficient food, and nearly

50% of the female members among all the social groups eat the leftover food.

It is also argued that food energy intake is a poor measure of nutritional status for the reason that it not only depends on nutrient intake but on non-nutrition food attributes, privately and publicly provided inputs and health status also influence malnutrition (Radhakrishna et al., 2004). Another way of looking at the intra-household differences in consumption of food and across social groups is to analyze food security with the help of anthropometric measures.

Nutritional status of individuals is assessed by means of the BMI. It is computed by using the weight and height of the individual ($BMI = \text{weight}/\text{height}^2$). A BMI value less than 16 is an indication of severe malnutrition and a BMI less than 18.5 and more than 16 reflects moderate malnutrition. For the children below 5 years we have used two measures i.e., low weight-for-height which reflects wasting and low height-for-age reflects the stunting (chronic undernutrition). From Table 7 it is clear that majority of the SC and ST households suffer with malnutrition in both the villages.

Table 7: Nutritional status in Karumanchi and Odipilavancha (in percent %)

Karumanchi Nutritional statuses in terms of BMI	SC		ST		OBC		Others	
	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M
Undernourishment (<16)	60.0	33.3	64.0	56.0	37.1	20.4	26.0	15.9
Normal (18.5- 22.9)	40.0	66.7	36.0	44.0	62.9	80.8	74.0	84.1
Odipilavancha Undernourishment (<16)	62.1	39.2	68.8	57.8	28.0	21.5	22.2	20.0
Normal (18.5- 22.9)	37.9	60.8	31.2	42.2	72	78.5	77.8	80.0

Source: Field survey, 2018.

Table 8: Nutritional status of children below 5years in Karumanchi and Odipilavancha (in percent %)

	Stunting	Wasting
Karumanchi	22.8	16.9
Odipilavancha	24.3	19.3

Source: Field survey, 2018.

Inequality as an underlying factor for food insecurity

Access to Land and Inequality across Social Groups

Land is often recognized as a tool of socio-economic empowerment. Access to land is one of the important indicators of better living standards in rural areas and an important indicator of food security.

Land Distribution and Ownership in Odipilavancha:

Table 9: Size and Class-wise Distribution of Household Ownership among Various Social Groups at Odipilavancha

NSSO Classification		In acres (approx.)	SC	ST	OBC	Others
0	Landless	0	92	12	28	3
0.001-0.004	Near Landless	0.002 - 0.009	0	0	0	0
0.005-0.40	Marginal	0.012-0.99	21	6	9	0
0.41-1.00	Small	1.01-2.47	60	8	18	4
1.01-2.00	Semi-Medium	2.5 - 4.94	25	3	16	10
2.01-4.00	Medium	5.00 - 9.88	14	3	8	13
4.01 & Above	Large	9.9 - and above	3	0	3	11
Total	All	All sizes	215	32	82	41

Source: Field survey, 2018.

Land ownership and distribution amongst various social groups at Odipilavancha reveals a skewed distribution of land with land concentration amongst fewer social groups, and dispossession

being attributed to a vast majority. The feature of landlessness is exhibited more amongst SC, followed by Other Backward Classes (OBCs) and then followed by Scheduled Tribes (ST), the last being Others which includes dominant caste households. Tables 9 and 10 provide the details of access to land and ownership by social groups in Odipilavancha village.

Table 10: Size and Class Wise Distribution of Land Ownership among Various Social Groups at Odipilavancha

NSSO Classification		In acres (approx.)	SC	ST	OBC	Other
0	Landless	0	0	0	0	0
0.001-0.004	Near Landless	0.002 - 0.009	0	0	0	0
0.005-0.40	Marginal	0.012-0.99	8.03	1.68	4.6	0
0.41-1.00	Small	1.01-2.47	84	11.6	29.5	5.5
1.01-2.00	Semi- Medium	2.5 - 4.94	81.3	9.5	59	32.5
2.01-4.00	Medium	5.00 - 9.88	87.05	19.25	49.5	96
4.01 & Above	Large	9.9 - and above	31	0	40	141
Total			291.38	42.03	182.6	275

Source: Field survey, 2018.

An elaborate account of skewed distribution can be observed by comparing the ownership of land by various social groups with their proportion of households amongst total households. The unequal distribution of land amongst various social groups is best analyzed through a comparative assessment of SC vis-à-vis other castes in Table 11. The striking gap in ownership of land amongst social groups explains the persisting inequality and skewed distribution of land amongst various social groups at Odipilavancha.

Table 11: Land and Household Proportion of various households among various social groups at Odipilavancha

	SC	ST	OBC	Others	All
Proportion of Households	58.1	8.6	22.1	11.0	100.0
Proportion of ownership of Land	36.8	5.3	23.0	34.7	100.0
Average Size of Land Owned	1.36	1.31	2.23	6.71	2.14

Source: Field survey, 2018.

Figure 2: Lorenz Distribution of Land ownership amongst various social groups at Odipilavancha

Gini-Coefficient values for SC-0.672234, ST-0.678526, OBC-0.623701, others-0.362129 and ALL-0.66493.

Inequality in distribution of ownership of land amongst various social groups at Odipilavancha has been mapped in the figure through Lorenz distribution. It is observed that SC and ST are the groups which are far distanced from the Line of Equality/ Line of Equal distribution, followed by OBCs and Other castes. Gini Coefficients were calculated to estimate quantum of inequality,

the figures reveal that there is a greater amount of inequality in the case of SC, ST and OBCs as compared with other castes as shown in Figure 2.

Land Distribution and Ownership in Karumanchi:

In the village of Karumanchi, ownership of land presents a large-scale inequality in distribution of ownership of land among various social groups. There is absolute inequality in terms of land ownership for ST, while relative inequality is observed in the case of SC and OBCs as compared with other castes. The unequal distribution of ownership of land can be understood by looking at comparative analysis of proportion of households and ownership of land as given in Tables 12 and 13.

Table 12: Size and Class wise distribution of household ownership among Various Social Groups at Karumanchi

NSSO Classification		In acres (approx.)	SC	ST	OBC	Others
0	Landless	0	343	38	127	45
0.001-0.004	Near Landless	0.002 - 0.009	0	0	0	0
0.005-0.40	Marginal	0.012-0.99	3	0	1	1
0.41-1.00	Small	1.01-2.47	24	0	16	5
1.01-2.00	Semi-Medium	2.5 - 4.94	23	0	6	25
2.01-4.00	Medium	5.00 - 9.88	4	0	8	17
4.01 & Above	Large	9.9- and above	5	0	5	46
Total			402	38	163	139
N.R. (not responded)						4

Source: Field survey, 2018.

Table 13: Size and Class Wise Distribution of Land Ownership among Various Social Groups at Karumanchi

NSSO Classification		In acres (approx.)	SC	ST	OBC	Other
0	Landless	0	0	0	0	0
0.001-0.004	Near Landless	0.002 - 0.009	0	0	0	0
0.005-0.40	Marginal	0.012-0.99	1.5	0	0.6	0.5
0.41-1.00	Small	1.01-2.47	40	0	26	6.75
1.01-2.00	Semi-Medium	2.5 - 4.94	79	0	19	91.65
2.01-4.00	Medium	5.00 - 9.88	30	0	47	103.7
4.01 & Above	Large	9.9 - and above	75	0	68	1019
Total			225.5	0	160.6	1221.6

Source: Field survey, 2018.

The unequal distribution in terms of ownership of land is mapped in Lorenz curve in Table 14 and Figure 3, the Lorenz curve for ST reveals 100% inequality, while the Lorenz distribution for SC is far away from line of equi-distribution. OBCs and Other castes is comparatively nearer to the line of equi-distribution. The Gini-Coefficient presents the scale of inequality clearly in table 14.

Table 14: Household and Land Ownership among various Social Groups at Karumanchi

Social Category	No. of Households	Proportion of Households	Area Owned (in acres)	Proportion of Area Owned	Average Area Owned Per Household
SC	402	54.1	225.5	14.0	0.56
ST	38	5.1	0	0	0
OBC	163	21.9	160.6	9.9	0.98
Others	139	18.7	1221.6	75.9	8.79
All	742	100.0	1607.7	100.0	2.17

Source: Field survey, 2018.

Figure 3: Lorenz Distribution of Land ownership among various social groups at Karumanchi

Gini coefficients of respective social groups are SC-0.914767, ST-1 (Owing to absolute inequality the Gini-Coefficient for ST stands at 1) OBC-0.876208, others-0.568135 and All-0.86797 (Field survey, 2018).

From the above analysis it is very clear that most of the marginalized farmers hold less than two acres of land in Odipilavancha and less than one acre in Karumanchi. There exists high inequality among the various social group farmers in terms of access to land in Karumanchi compared to Odipilavancha. Basic crops cultivated at Karumanchi are Bengal gram, and tobacco, while paddy and cotton are cultivated in Odipilavancha.

Till the 1980's paddy was the most dominant crop in both villages, but now Tobacco, Bengal gram dominate the cropping patterns at Karumanchi, a shifting pattern to cotton observed at Odipilavancha. The farmers refer to the fact that the returns on paddy were not so attractive, whereas Tobacco, Bengal gram and cotton has more demand in the nearby markets. In addition to this, the water sources are also not sufficient for paddy cultivation. The

change in the cropping system and climate affected the agricultural labour households by reducing the employment and the number of working days. The major source of income in both the villages is from agriculture cultivation 60.71% in Odipilavancha and 71.76% in Karumanchi.

Expenditure pattern across Social Groups

SC and ST households spend around 39% and 46% respectively on food in the total income, while non-food expenditure (including health and education expenditure) is around 60.73% of total expenditure in Odipilavancha. More non-food expenditure implies that OBC and Others are spending more on education. This result tallies with our macro data (NSSO -MPCE) at State level, which implies that the gap in terms of mean consumption expenditure between the SC and ST social groups and the others are increasing over a period of time, which indicates increasing economic inequalities across social groups and differences in access to education.

It is very clear from the data and field observation that most of the SC and ST social group children go to government schools or they work as child labour, whereas other social group children mostly go to private schools, and hence their expenditure on education is high. There exists a large income gap between various social groups in both the villages. In this context, it is interesting to see the access to credit by various social groups. Access to credit at affordable cost positively affects the productivity, asset formation, income and food security of the rural poor. The major concern of the government is to bring all the rural households within the banking fold and promote complete financial inclusion.

Table 15: Consumption Expenditure among various Social Groups at Odipilavancha (in percent %)

Social Group	SC	ST	OBC	Others	Total
Food Expenditure	39.28	46.23	40.92	34.97	39.50
Education Expenditure	6.52	6.08	13.09	16.36	10.19
Health Expenditure	17.24	14.77	12.72	14.04	15.16
Non-Food Expenditure*	36.97	32.92	33.27	34.63	35.15
Total Expenditure	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Total number of households	198 (56.41)	32 (9.12)	81 (23.08)	40 (11.39)	351 (100)

Note:
 *Tobacco, intoxicants fuel, light, clothing, bedding, footwear, and rent to the house

Source: Field survey, 2017, and 2018.

Table 16: Consumption Expenditure among various Social Groups at Karumanchi (in percent %)

Social Group	SC	ST	OBC	Others	Total
Total Food Expenditure	50.57	54.42	48.49	33.28	45.66
Education Expenditure	8.48	1.00	8.69	26.02	12.93
Health Expenditure	10.34	17.22	12.38	13.15	11.78
Non-Food Expenditure	30.61	27.36	30.44	27.55	29.63
Total Expenditure	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Total No.of Households	402 (54)	38 (5.11)	163 (21.94)	139 (18.71)	742 (100)

Source: Field survey, 2017 and 2018.

It is clear from the above Table 17 even now in rural areas marginalized groups depend more on non-institutional credit. Lack of access to land and credit makes the marginalized groups to remain in poverty and food insecurity. In this context, state support policies play an important role in reducing the poverty and food insecurity at household level. Majority of the poor in rural Andhra Pradesh and Telangana depend on PDS for their food security at household level. Possessing a ration card/Aadhar is an important step towards accessing the PDS and buying from it.

During 2013-14 in Andhra Pradesh, 215.5 lakh white cards were there between 2004 and 2014; all government benefits were linked with ration cards. They were eligible for free treatment in private and corporate hospitals under Aarogyasri, free education in colleges, free houses, claims of up to Rs. 3 lakh under CMRF for medical treatment etc. After the bifurcation of the state to Telangana and Andhra Pradesh, Telangana state has issued the food security cards in the place of ration cards.

In both the villages, majority of the SC and ST households depend on PDS for their rice consumption. In case of SC households, 48.2% of total consumption of rice is from PDS and that of ST households is 89.1% in Karumanchi. In Odipilavancha village also, similar trend is observed. Interestingly, others and OBC households depend more on home production and open market in both the villages, because of their access to land. In the village more than 50% of the households spend around one to two hours to fetch their PDS allocations. The quantities of rice supplied to poor households is 5 kg of rice per person per month subject to a ceiling of 25 kg. In Telangana state it is 6 kg per person per month subject to a ceiling of 30 kg. Many times, this is inadequate compared to their consumption requirements.

Table 17: Sources of consumption of rice per household (in percent %)

Social Groups	Karumanchi				Odipilavancha			
	SC	ST	OBC	Others	SC	ST	OBC	Others
Home Production	11.7	-	42.8	62.8	11	5.6	73.8	75.3
PDS	48.2	89.1	33.8	24.7	40.8	74.9	14.5	10.3
Open market	40.0	10.9	23.2	12.3	48.0	19.5	11.6	14.2

Source: Field survey, 2018.

It was observed from the focus group discussions that PDS rice consumption is influenced by the factors such as, family size, occupation, landholding and wage rate. The extent of PDS support declines with expenditure levels of the households and land size.

For the low-income households, agricultural labour households, landless and for marginal farmer households, PDS rice and other items such as oil and sugar consumption are an important source of calorie intake.

In both the villages, majority of the households hold the ration cards. Targeting errors that includes exclusion and inclusion errors exist in both the villages. We found more exclusion errors than inclusion errors. About 28.4% (Karumanchi) and 36.1% (Odipilavancha) of the poor households are excluded from the PDS/food security safety nets. With high exclusion errors, it comes out clearly that PDS is not benefiting all the poor households.

The basic purpose of the food security act is to transfer income to the poor by supplying essential commodities at subsidized prices, but this seems to bypass a large section due to social engineering process. Inefficient targeting will have impact on income gains through the PDS at household level and which in turn would influence the consumption at individual level. In order to understand the magnitude of the income transfer in rice distribution by the PDS, we have calculated the income transfers to the household.

The income gain of villagers from the rice scheme depends upon the coverage of the PDS, quantities supplied through the PDS and the difference between the open market price and the ration price. Monthly per capita income gain, which is calculated using the difference between open market price and ration shop price is Rs.19.00 per person per month in Odipilavancha and in Karumanchi Rs.22.70 per person per month. From 2004-05 to 2011-12, there has been a substantial increase in the implicit income transfer to households which has a significant impact on reducing the poverty (Dreze and Khera, 2015).

Most of the households depend on PDS for the rice consumption. The percentage of households reporting consumption of rice from PDS during a 30-day period rose sharply

from 24.4% to 39% in rural India and from 13% to 20.5% in urban India between 2004-05 and 2009-10. The major states with relatively high incidence of PDS purchase of rice in the rural sector were Tamil Nadu (89.65%), Andhra Pradesh (86.36%), Karnataka (75.02%), and Chhattisgarh (60.84%), followed by Kerala and Odisha (55.26%), and Maharashtra (44.22%).

Social vulnerability

All the indicators of demographic, economic and social indices are measured in different scales. It was necessary to normalize each indicator for an index. Here, the study has used the procedures of normalization as followed in Iyengar and Sudarshan (1982). If the “overall social vulnerability” increases with the increase in the value(s) of indicator(s), the following normalization procedure is used.

$$IndexK_f = (K_f - K_{min}) / (K_{max} - K_{min}) \quad (1)$$

If the “overall social vulnerability” decreases with the increase in value(s) of indicator(s), the following procedure is used.

$$IndexK_f = (K_{max} - K_f) / (K_{max} - K_{min}) \quad (2)$$

Where K_f is the original value of sub-component for each farm group and K_{max} and K_{min} are the minimum and maximum values of each sub-component determined using data from all farm and caste groups of respective villages. For variables that show frequencies, for example, the percentage of farmers who have changed their crops, the minimum value was set at 0 and maximum value at 100. After each indicator was normalized, the indicators are averaged to find out the value of each major component following the equation (3).

$$K_h = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Index}_f^i}{n} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where K_h is one of the three components of farm and caste groups, that is, demographic, economic and social components. Index_f^i represents “the sub-components indexed by i , which make up for each major component, and n is the number of sub-components in each major component.” Once the index values of demographic, economic and social factors are calculated, the social vulnerability (SV) of all farm groups and caste groups in their respective village will be found out as follows:

$$SV = f \cdot [1/n(K_{DF} + K_{EF} + K_{SF})] \quad (4)$$

where, K_{DF} , K_{EF} and K_{SF} are the index values of the demographic, economic and social factors, and n = the number of factors (major components) of social vulnerability.

The marginal and small farmers’ groups are more vulnerable to the effects of climate change and variability than the medium and large farmers’ groups in both the villages. The study reveals that the higher relative social vulnerability of marginal and small farm groups over other groups is attributed to the greater vulnerabilities of demographic, economic and social factors.

Social vulnerability among different social groups, highlights two important aspects – (i) overall social vulnerability is high in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana villages (ii) the SC and ST households are more vulnerable to climate change effects than OBC and Other caste households in both the selected villages due to high vulnerabilities for demographic, economic and social factors.

Table 18: Farm size –wise and Social group-wise Vulnerability in the two selected villages

Components	Marginal	Small	Medium	Large	All	SC	ST	OBC	OC	All
Karumanchi Village (AP)										
Demographic	0.658	0.559	0.422	0.335	0.455	0.665	0.712	0.499	0.501	0.599
Economic	0.794	0.774	0.399	0.301	0.599	0.887	0.704	0.521	0.288	0.501
Social	0.801	0.799	0.562	0.499	0.642	0.888	0.882	0.234	0.087	0.508
Odipilavancha Village (Telangana State)										
Demographic	0.665	0.588	0.421	0.323	0.467	0.721	0.702	0.442	0.444	0.543
Economic	0.772	0.702	0.376	0.299	0.576	0.899	0.871	0.499	0.301	0.523
Social	0.799	0.789	0.501	0.487	0.589	0.889	0.877	0.201	0.079	0.501

Conclusion

Food-security at micro-level has quite a few important dimensions including social group, gender, non-food expenditure and nutritional security. We have attempted an investigation of these issues by utilizing the household level data of the selected villages.

Social factors do play an important role in food and nutritional security, lower the caste higher the deprivation which in turn influences their bargaining power in the labour market leading to lower access to income. Total income of the household is an important variable in explaining the changes in access to food at household level. Access to land is essential to ensure the right to food. Majority of the SC and ST households are small and marginal farmers.

Despite fulfilling the eligibility criteria, some households were not issued ration cards. For example, some families were struck off the PDS list during the rollout of the National Food Security Act (NFSA) in the states. An important reason could be the cap on the total number of beneficiaries allowed under this scheme. Distribution of food grains play an important role in providing the food security at household level. Poor households

with no ration card/food security card are at a higher risk of food insecurity compared to households with white cards. Calorie consumption levels of SC and ST households are very low among all the social groups. This is reflected in terms of BMI for adults and stunting for children.

In essence, the food and nutrition insecurity are strongly intertwined in the caste and class characteristics of the households. Therefore, overlooking these dimensions food and nutrition security aspects cannot be adequately addressed. There also prevails intra-household food and nutrition insecurity where the women of the households are at the receiving end. Food and nutrition insecurity research and policy need clear articulation of intersectionality of gender with caste and class dimensions in agrarian context.

(Funding: This paper is a part of ICSSR Major Research project titled "Climate Change and Persistence of Food and Nutrition Security: A Case of Vulnerable Groups" and IOE Grant of University of Hyderabad for project titled "Understanding and Addressing Food and Nutrition Security issues among Vulnerable Groups: An Inter-disciplinary study in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana").

The initial version of this paper was presented in INSEE-CESS International Conference on "Climate Change and Disasters: Challenges, opportunities and responses, the Tenth INSEE Biennial Conference, 6-8 November, 2019.

The authors thank all the respondents of Karumanchi and Odipilanvacha villages).

References

- Achanta, A. N. 1993. 'An assessment of the potential impact of global warming on Indian rice production', in (ed.) Achanta A.N., *The Climate Change Agenda: An Indian Perspective*, TERI, New Delhi.
- Adger, W.N. 1999. "Social Vulnerability to Climate Change and Extreme in Coastal Vietnam", *World Development*, 27(2): 249-69.

Malnutrition and Inequality among the Vulnerable Social Groups

Sridevi, Jyotishi and Prashanth

doi:

- Adger, W.N., and P.M. Kelly. 1999. "Social Vulnerability to Climate Change and the Architecture of Entitlements". *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 4:253-66.
- Agarwal, B.1990. "Social Security and the Family in Rural India: Coping with Seasonality and Calamity", *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 17: 341-412.
- Aggarwal, P. K. and N. Kalra. 1994. "Simulating the effect of climatic factors, genotype and management on productivity of wheat in India", *Indian Agricultural Research Institute Publication*, New Delhi, India: 156.
- Aggarwal, P. K. and R.K. Mall. 2002. 'Climate change and rice yields in diverse agroenvironments of India. II. Effect of uncertainties in scenarios and crop models on impact assessment'. *Climatic Change* 52(3): 331-343.
- Aggarwal, P. K. and S.K. Sinha.1993. "Effect of probable increase in carbon dioxide and temperature on productivity of wheat in India", *Journal of Agricultural Meteorology*, 48(5): 811-814.
- Anand, S and A. Sen. 1994. "Human Development Index: Methodology and Measurement, Occasional Papers, Human Development Report Office, New York.
- Auffhammer, M., V.Ramanathan and J.R. Vincent. 2006. "Integrated Model Shows that Atmospheric Brown Cloud and GHGs have Reduced Rice Harvests in India", *PNAS*, 103 (52): 19668-19672.
- Balasubramanian T.N., Arivudai Nambi A., Paul D. 2009 A suggested index for assessment of vulnerability of a location to climate change. *Journal of Agrometeorology*, 9(2):129- 137.
- Bouis, Howarth. 2008. *Rising Food Prices will Result in Severe Declines in Mineral and Vitamin Intakes of the Poor*, Harvestplus, IFPRI, Washington, D.C.
- Brenkert A.L., and E.L. Malone.2005. Modeling vulnerability and resilience to climate change: a case study of India and Indian states. *Climate Change*, 72:57-102.
- Brook, N., 2003. *Vulnerability, risk and adaptation: A conceptual framework*, Working Paper No. 38, Tyndall Centre for Climate Change Research, University of East Anglia, Norwich.
- Datt, G and M. Ravallion. 1998. "Farm Productivity and Rural Poverty in India", *Journal of Development Studies*, 34(4):62-85.
- Deressa T., Hassan R.M., Ringler C. 2008. *Measuring Ethiopian farmers' vulnerability to climate change across regional states*. IFPRI Discussion Paper No. 806, Washington.
- Deshpande R. S. and Amalendu Jyotishi. 2002. "Managing Ground Water Resource on Deccan Plateau: Pani Panchayat as an Institution of Collective Action" in (ed.) Dinesh Marothia, *Institutionalising Common Pool Resources*, Concept Publishers, New Delhi.
- Deshpande R. S. and Amalendu Jyotishi. 2005. *The State Policy and Poverty in India: An Understanding in Retrospective*, *Indian Social Science Review*, 7(2): 281-298.
- Eswaran, M., A. Kotwal et al.2008. "How Does Poverty Decline? Suggestive Evidence from India, 1983-1999", *Bread Policy Papers*.

- Food and Agriculture Organization, 2001, The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2006. FAO, Rome.
- Food and Agriculture Organization. 1997. World Development Indicators. FAO, Rome.
- Food and Agriculture Organization. 2002. The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2001. FAO, Rome.
- Food and Agriculture Organization. 2013. Food Insecurity in the World the multiple dimensions of food security. FAO, Rome.
- Gangadhar Rao, D. and Sinha, S. K. 1994. Impact of climate change on simulated wheat production in India, in (eds.) C. Rosenzweig and I. Iglesias, Implications of Climate Change for International Agriculture: Crop Modelling Study. USEPA230-B-94003. USEPA, Washington, DC. 1–17.
- IIPS. 2017. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4), 2015–16: India. International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS), Mumbai.
- IIPS. 2020. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–20: Andhra Pradesh International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS), Mumbai.
- Jean Drèze and Reetika Khera. 2015. Understanding Leakages in the Public Distribution System, Economic and Political Weekly, 50(7): 39–42.
- Patnaik, U., and Narayanan, K. 2015. How effective are coping mechanisms in securing livelihoods against climatic aberrations? Evidences from rural India. International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management, 7(3): 359–374.
- Radhakrishna, R., Rao, K.H. Ravi, C. and Reddy, B.S. 2004. Chronic poverty and malnutrition in India. Working Paper 11. New Delhi: CPRC-IIPA.
- Sridevi Gummadi, Amalendu Jyotishi, Jagadeesh and Venkateswarlu. 2018. “Climate Change Vulnerability and Agrarian Communities in Temporal and Spatial Context: District Wise Analysis of Undivided Andhra Pradesh”, Man and Development, 60(1): 29–46.
- Sukhatme, P. V. 1980. Nutrition policy: need for reorientation. Economic and Political Weekly, 15(26): 1101–1105.
- UNICEF. (2019). The State of the World's Children 2019: Children, food and nutrition: Growing well in a changing world. UNICEF.
- Von Grebmer, K., J. Bernstein, R. Alders, O. Dar, R. Kock, F. Rampa, M. Wiemers, K. Acheampong, A. Hanano, B. Higgins, R. Ní Chéilleachair, C. Foley, S. Gitter, K. Ekstrom, and H. Fritschel. 2020. 2020 Global Hunger Index: One Decade to Zero Hunger: Linking Health and Sustainable Food Systems. Bonn: Welthungerhilfe; and Dublin: Concern Worldwide.
- Yadav, D. K., and Barve, A. 2017. Analysis of socioeconomic vulnerability for cyclone affected communities in coastal Odisha, India. International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction, 22: 387–396.